

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 4(13)

IV. 2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD, dotsent

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

 [@fer_teach_uz](https://t.me/fer_teach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya

L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston

THE PROBLEM OF FORMATION OF THE CREATIVE ABILITY OF STUDENTS OF ARTISTIC POTTERY IN THE HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

Islamova Shodiya Gayratjon qizi

Namangan State University, Faculty of Pedagogy Art Pottery, 4th year student

Buvayev Vokhobjon Sodikovich

*Namangan State University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine and Applied Arts,
Associate Professor*

Abstract. *In this article, creativity in the process of pottery training, development of creative competence of pedagogues, introduction to the processes of creating artworks, innovative activities of students, preparation of future potters in the higher education system, interactive education, innovative education and information- communication technologies, factors that develop students' creativity skills are described.*

Keywords. *Applied art, ceramic creativity, ceramic technology, artistic ceramics, European equivalents, Architectural art, ceramics, creativity, painting, skills, interactive methods, innovation, education*

ПРОБЛЕМА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ГОНЧАРНОГО ДЕЛА В ВЫСШЕМ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ.

Исламова Шодия Гайратжон кызы

*Наманганский государственный университет, факультет педагогики
художественной керамики, студент 4 курса*

Буваев Вохобжон Содикович

*Наманганский государственный университет, педагогический факультет, кафедра
изобразительного и прикладного искусства, доцент*

Аннотация. *В данной статье творчество в процессе обучения гончарному делу, развитие творческой компетентности педагогов, знакомство с процессами создания художественных произведений, инновационная деятельность студентов, подготовка будущих гончаров в системе высшего образования, интерактивное образование, инновационное образование и информационно-Описаны коммуникативные технологии, факторы, развивающие творческие способности студентов.*

Ключевые слова. *Прикладное искусство, керамическое творчество, керамическая технология, художественная керамика, европейские эквиваленты, Архитектурное искусство, керамика, творчество, живопись, навыки, интерактивные методы, инновации, образование.*

Introduction. Pottery, Pottery is a type of craft that makes various objects from clay (terracotta, earthenware, building materials). The main raw material in pottery is soil. The process of making different types of pottery from clays of different origin and composition. People have been engaged in pottery since the Neolithic period. Special clay products are made by hand, dried and heated in a fire. Pottery is one of the types of applied folk art, and it belongs to the field of crafts that makes various objects, dishes, building materials from clay. The main raw material in pottery is natural soil, and the longer the clay is baked, the better the quality of the pottery. The art of tiling, which is the decorative art of pottery, has developed widely in the architecture of Central Asia. The availability of clay used in pottery in all parts of the world ensured the widespread use of pottery in almost all nations. At first, women were engaged in pottery, and with the appearance of the pottery wheel, men were also involved in this work. Dishes were cooked in special ovens and steam ovens. Simple methods of pottery still exist among the peoples living in the mountainous regions of Asia. Excavated remains of Neolithic settlements show that during that period the vessels were made with pointed bottoms (vessels were pressed into the ground). In the Eneolithic period, the production of elegant pottery and the use of pottery in architecture flourished in the countries of the East, in Greece. As glazing techniques were discovered, the artistic value of pottery increased. From the 20s of the 20th century, attention was paid to the externalization of pottery. Experimental pottery was opened in Tashkent, pottery workshops were opened in Samarkand, educational production, art workshop was launched in Tashkent (1932), short-term courses were organized, potters were trained and their skills improved. Potters such as T. Miraliyev (Tashkent), R. Egamberdiyev, A. Hazratkulov (Shahrisabz), Muhammad Siddiq, Usman Umarov (Gijduvan) taught young people.

People's Artist of Uzbekistan Muhyiddin Rahimov has made a great contribution to the research and development of pottery and the preparation of potters from young people. Pottery is one of the oldest and most interesting types of folk art of Uzbekistan. There are many main schools and centers of pottery in our country. Rishton, Bukhara, Gurumsarai, Tashkent, Khorezm, Samarkand and Kashkadarya pottery schools can be counted. These pottery schools differ from each other in the way of making the products, patterns, colors and finish.

Literature analysis and methodologies. The Uzbek people are famous all over the world for their ancient and rich culture. Ancient monuments and the underground part of Uzbekistan are a huge historical museum. Every architectural

monument in Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Khiva, Termiz and other cities is a great work, rare manuscripts, examples of folk art, testify to the high culture of the Uzbek people at that time. For example, buildings built by our ancestors, architectural decorations, their variety, geometric and plant-like patterns, composite images, all our monuments invite to enjoy and aesthetic education. Through them, our ancestors expressed their hopes and dreams to the people. Our cultural wealth acquired over the centuries, some types of folk art, their specific types, real Uzbek names, work technologies and the names of our masters who created them are slowly on the verge of being forgotten. Therefore, preserving, appreciating and using the historical monuments and other monuments of our applied art created as a result of the creative work of our people over the centuries is one of the most important tasks of the present era.

Students of the "Art Pottery" department should have the following knowledge.

- the methodology and principles of teaching pottery art in lyceums, schools and colleges:

- Content and purpose of the national personnel training program of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- use of didactic principles in teaching methodology of "art pottery".

Students should develop the following skills in this subject:

- organization of educational processes;

- problematic organization of the subject;

- best practices methodology;

- the methodology of teaching the art of "artistic pottery";

Discussion and results. Ceramic art, like other disciplines, has its own characteristics and terms. But this dictionary of art has not been created. Thousands of young people in Uzbekistan face certain difficulties in learning the secrets of artistic pottery. In the main areas of higher education reform, it is necessary to "develop a sense of beauty, form a healthy artistic taste, and develop the ability to correctly understand and appreciate works of art, beauty and wealth." " is called. Mother Nature." In fact, there are explanatory dictionaries that are currently in high demand. Students of Art Secrets encounter a lot of concepts and terms in the process of reading, it is difficult to find such terms and concepts in the relevant literature at any time. For example , in the interesting pamphlet "Sanatim-bakhtim" by the national artist of Uzbekistan Mahmud Usmanov, there are a number of motivational terms, namely: "hashti tufсор, sarnigon, tufсорi wing, crane wing, house decorator, hasti davra, chorsar, round star, shashdona, parrak, lola islami, bafta islami, free islami, turunj, bandi rumi, islami guldona, islami

madohil, lola hoshiya" and other terms are given, but the dictionary meaning of these terms can be found in the relevant books.

Some of the terms created during the creative activity of the Uzbek people are being forgotten, in the process of reading brochures, articles, documents and archive materials, there are many words in them, hundreds of our phrases, we are written differently. see used in meanings. Some research has been done to eliminate the diversity in such expressions. For example, when we asked students to answer questions with potters, they could not clearly state the dictionary meaning of many terms found in folk art. For example, among such terms: morpech, kundal, ruta, madokhil, minqar, Islamic duraftor, namoen, etc. This shows that the terms of pottery art have been studied very little on a scientific basis. First of all, it is advisable to open the column "Folk practical ornaments" in the newspapers and magazines of our republic and enrich your vocabulary with art, and secondly, to create a scientifically based explanatory dictionary of folk decorative arts. Genres called nature art, artistic pottery or aesthetic art all have their own characteristics. They are mainly based on the depiction of natural scenes, people or animals, and have characteristics that strive to create a sought-after feeling. Artistic pottery is based on the production of the best and aesthetic spectacles of people. Artistic pottery, which includes an international orientation, actively participates in the purpose of uniting humanity by making communication between people.

Summary. In short, artistic pottery is a masterpiece of folk decorative art that has been carefully preserved by our ancestors for centuries. These types of applied arts, preserved in history and to this day, will be more appreciated and respected in the future. After all, unique patterns carved, drawn, scratched, and painted are an expression of human perception and human feelings. Bamisoli is a song of life written in black clay. and the song of life rings from time to time. Our huge cultural wealth created over the centuries, in particular, the unique aspects of the widespread types of Uzbek national artistic pottery, schools, execution techniques, and the blessed names of the masters who created them, are on the verge of disappearing forever. . Therefore, it is important to preserve these unique art masterpieces and teach them to young people. Ceramic art is a culture that is acceptable to a wide range of people, combining several arts (pen, painting, music, dramatic arts, etc.) and connecting it with human spirit and spirituality. lays Achievements such as the initial reference to these art forms, the control of human activity, the principles of relevance of creativity, the power of human emotions, and the ability to be a unique child are important. Pottery is about gaining value, bringing out the best in people, encouraging creative behavior, bringing all the

looks and colors to life. The art of ceramic art is related to the formation of creative abilities of students. This art form is important for the development of culture, creativity and aesthetic skills. Art pottery helps us to express students' learning, creative thinking and personal historical information. In this article, the art of pottery is important for students, as it is necessary to develop their ways of self-expression and creative exploration, and to pass on folk crafts to the next generation.

References:

1. M.Rahimov. O'zbekiston badiiy keramikasi. T., 1961 y.
2. E.Xoxlova. Badiiy keramika. M., 1978 y.
3. V.Xaxlov. Badiiy keramika asoslari. S., 1988 y.
4. E.Sayko. Keramika ishlab chiqarish texnikasi va texnologiyasining tarixiy taraqqiyoti. M., 1982 y.
5. A.Turg'unov. O'zbek kulolchiligi san'atining hududiy xususiyatlari. T. 2001.
6. Рўзинов, Б. А., Нуриддинов, Б. Х., & Умаров, Х. Фарғона водийси амалий санъатининг таълим тарбиядаги ўрни.
7. Umarov, X. (2023). The role of the type of applied art in architectural monuments (on the example of the hojaamin grave complex). *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3), 182-187.
8. Шарипжонов, М., & Икромова, М. Д. (2018). Tasviriy san'atda animalizm janri. *Научное знание современности*, (5), 94-96.
9. oglu Sharipjonov, M. S. Oliy pyedagogik ta'limda talabalarga muammoli mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish texnologiyalari.
10. Temirova, M. (2023). The ability of the teacher to apply the technologies of individual work when teaching students the lessons of skillful painting. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3), 177-181.
11. Темирова, М. И. (2022). Изобразительное искусство и его содержательная сущность. *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches*, 1(2).
12. Temirova Muqaddas, & Turg'unboyeva Maftunaxon. (2023). Tasviriy san'at fanlarini maktablarda o'qitishning zamonaviy texnologiyalari. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10337479>
13. Temirova Muqaddas, & Nazarov Murodjon. (2023). Mahobatli rangtasvir kompozitsiyasining zamonaviy uslublari, shakllarini talabalariga o'qitishda yangicha yondashuv. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10322777>
14. Amanullaev, A. (2022). Specific factors of comprehensive study and analysis of the history and culture of the uzbek people. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(02), 1-4.
15. Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). Current issues in the training of future teachers of fine arts. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(03), 1-3.
16. Абдимуминова, Д. А., & Амануллаев, А. А. (2018). Использование традиций этики "устоз-шогирид"(мастер и ученик) на занятиях прикладного искусства. *NovaInfo. Ru*, 2(85), 203-206

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro'yxatidan (№ 078777) o'tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay'ati a'zolidan respublikaning turli OTMLarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o'rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 04. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 04. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 04. | 2024

Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyligi uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.

